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INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO TEACHING TRANSLATION IN HIGHER
EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. Translation studies have become an essential part of language education in today's interconnected world. This article explores the variety of teaching methods employed in higher education institutions to develop skilled translators. Focusing on contemporary pedagogical approaches, the article highlights the importance of integrating digital tools, interdisciplinary learning, and adaptive pedagogies to better prepare students for the evolving demands of the translation industry. Approaches such as blended learning, collaborative projects, contextualized translation tasks, and specialized training for niche fields are examined to demonstrate how translation education is evolving.

Key words: Blended learning, Contextualized translation tasks, Collaborative translation projects, Specialized training, Digital competency, Post-editing of machine translation (PEMT), Translation memory (TM), Interdisciplinary approaches.

ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ПРЕПОДАВАНИЮ ПЕРЕВОДА В ВЫСШИХ
УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЯХ

Аннотация. Исследования перевода стали неотъемлемой частью языкового образования в современном взаимосвязанном мире. В этой статье рассматривается разнообразие методов обучения, используемых в высших учебных заведениях для подготовки квалифицированных переводчиков. Сосредоточившись на современных педагогических подходах, статья подчеркивает важность интеграции цифровых инструментов, междисциплинарного обучения и адаптивной педагогики для лучшей подготовки студентов к меняющимся требованиям индустрии перевода. Такие подходы, как смешанное обучение, совместные проекты, контекстуализированные переводческие задачи и специализированное обучение для нишевых областей, рассматриваются для демонстрации того, как развивается переводческое образование.

Ключевые слова: смешанное обучение, контекстуализированные переводческие задачи, совместные переводческие проекты, специализированное обучение, цифровая

компетентность, постредактирование машинного перевода (PEMT), переводческая память (TM), междисциплинарные подходы.

In recent years, the methodology of teaching translation in higher education has undergone significant changes. As the translation profession adapts to technological advancements and global demand, educational institutions are revising traditional methods to better equip students with modern skills. While traditional teaching methods like task-based learning and contrastive analysis remain essential, new strategies such as digital tool integration, interdisciplinary collaboration, and contextualized learning are becoming increasingly prominent. The goal is to produce translators who are not only proficient in language but also adept at using technology and understanding the cultural contexts of their work.

Blended Learning in Translation Education

Blended learning, which combines online digital media with traditional classroom methods, is transforming translation teaching. This method offers flexibility, allowing students to access lectures, tutorials, and resources online while also participating in face-to-face workshops or seminars. In translation education, blended learning often incorporates the use of online translation platforms, machine translation tools, and databases for terminology management. This format allows students to engage in self-paced learning while also receiving personalized feedback in classroom settings. Instructors can guide students through complex translation challenges and ensure that they understand how to use Computer-Assisted Translation (CAT) tools effectively.

Blended learning prepares students for the dynamic translation environments they will encounter in the professional world.

Contextualized Translation Tasks

One of the newer methods being integrated into translation programs is contextualized translation. Rather than focusing solely on linguistic accuracy, this approach emphasizes the broader context in which translation occurs. Students are encouraged to analyze the purpose of a translation, the audience's needs, and the cultural significance of the source and target texts. For example, students may work on translating advertising materials, where cultural adaptation is crucial, or they might engage in subtitling, which requires not only accuracy but also brevity and timing. The goal is to ensure that students develop a functional understanding of translation as an intercultural and communicative act, rather than a purely linguistic one.[1]

Collaborative Translation Projects

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Collaboration has always been an important part of learning, and in translation education, it is gaining new prominence through group translation projects. These projects simulate real-world translation tasks where students must work in teams to manage large-scale or complex texts.

The process encourages students to divide roles, such as project manager, editor, and translator, mirroring the professional environment of translation agencies. Collaborative translation projects also provide students with the opportunity to engage in peer review, where they can evaluate and critique each other's work. This not only improves the quality of the translation but also fosters critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Additionally, by working in teams, students learn how to handle disagreements, manage time efficiently, and deliver consistent results.

Specialized Training for Niche Translation Fields

Higher education institutions are recognizing the growing demand for translators in specialized fields such as legal, medical, and technical translation. As a result, translation programs are offering targeted courses that focus on the unique requirements of these areas. Specialized training often involves both theoretical study and practical assignments that expose students to the terminological and stylistic demands of specific genres. For instance, a medical translation course might cover medical terminology, pharmaceutical texts, and patient records, while a legal translation course might delve into contract law, legal terminology, and court documents. The goal of these niche courses is to give students the tools they need to succeed in highly regulated and precise translation sectors, where mistakes can have serious consequences.

Digital Competency and the Use of Translation Technologies

In today's digital age, proficiency in translation technologies is essential for modern translators. Higher education institutions are increasingly incorporating digital tools and technologies into their curricula to reflect the realities of the translation profession. This includes teaching students to use CAT tools, translation memory software, and online terminology management platforms. Moreover, with the rise of machine translation systems such as Google Translate or DeepL, students are taught not only to use these tools but also to post-edit machine translations for accuracy and fluency. This skill, known as post-editing of machine translation (PEMT), is in high demand as the translation industry shifts toward greater reliance on automation.

Training students in digital competency ensures that they are able to integrate new technologies into their translation workflows, enhancing productivity and accuracy.

Interdisciplinary Approaches to Translation Education

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Another emerging trend is the interdisciplinary approach to translation education, which involves integrating knowledge from other fields such as law, business, or medicine into translation studies. By working alongside students from these disciplines or translating texts related to those fields, translation students gain insight into how language operates in specialized contexts.[3] For example, translation students may collaborate with law students to translate legal documents, gaining firsthand experience with the nuances of legal language. Similarly, partnerships with business or marketing departments allow translation students to engage in localization projects, where they adapt products, websites, or marketing materials to different cultural and linguistic contexts. This interdisciplinary model not only deepens students' understanding of the subject matter but also expands their ability to think critically across fields.

The methodology of teaching translation in higher education institutions is continuously evolving to meet the needs of a dynamic and globalized world. By incorporating blended learning, contextualized tasks, collaborative projects, specialized training, and digital tools, translation programs are better preparing students for the complexities of the modern translation industry. As translation becomes increasingly interdisciplinary, educators are also integrating knowledge from other fields, ensuring that students can navigate both linguistic and contextual challenges. Through these innovative approaches, students graduate not only as skilled translators but as professionals equipped to thrive in a technology-driven, multicultural world.

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